

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE NOVELS OF "JANE EYRE" AND " CHOLIKUSHI"

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Abstract: In this article, we will compare the famous work of Charlotta Bronte is “Jane Eyre”, who lived in the 19th century and left a bright mark in English literature, and the work of Turkish writer Rashod Nuri Guntekin, one of the most famous novel is “Cholikushi”, and observe the skill of the writers.

Key words: fate, orphan, “Cholikushi”, society, boarding house, equality, feminist.

Introduction

If we look at 19th century English literature, novels that reflect real social life events are important. As an example, we can cite the novel Jane Eyre by Charlotta Bronte. Jane Eyre is the story of a mistreated orphan. It is included that the life and wanderings of the poor girl Jane Eyre, the story of her struggle for her dignity against the background of the image of various sectors of society, the idea of equality of people, a woman’s right to her own life choice. So, I can say that not only “Cholikushi” is a romantic novel, but it is also important as a novel that skillfully critiques the social problems of the time. The novels tell about the fate of the young girl Feride. Additionally, it is not just a story about one fate, it is the story of an entire country during a period of rather painful metamorphoses and a change of eras: from the collapse of the Osman Empire to the emergence of the Turkish Republic.

Main body.

Charlotta Bronte’s novel “Jane Eyre” became famous all over the world. She took the image of protagonist Jane Eyre from herself. Bronte was medium of height, fragile, thin, not beautiful, but her features were not bad. She was a very intelligent

who did not have the feminine core of a woman at that time. We see the same girl on Jane Eyre. There are elements of Jane Eyre that echo Charlotte Brontë's own life. She and her sisters went to a school run by a headmaster as severe as Mr Brocklehurst. Two of Charlotte's sisters died there from tuberculosis (just like Jane's only friend, Helen Burns). Charlotte Brontë was also a governess for some years before turning to writing.

When we speak about Jane, we cannot ignore the fact that we are seeing one of the most famous feminist characters in history, probably one of the first feminist characters ever. Even though she is not constantly going over it, we get to see that she has strong moral convictions, and advanced ideas when it comes to the lives and the capacity of women. This shows up, for example, when she has to decide whether to stay with the man she loves and become his mistress, or leave him and find a respectable life somewhere else. She knows that leave is going to make her unhappy, but she also knows that she could never live knowing that she is acting against her principles.

I shouldn't forget to mention is that the novel is "Cholikushi" similar to "Jane Eyre". The novel tells about the fate of the young girl Feride. Having lost her mother as a child, she was assigned by her military father to the French boarding house "Notre Dame de Sion". Despite all the obstacles prepared for her by life, the main heroine of the novel, an orphan girl Feride, managed to overcome all difficulties and achieve her goals. Since this novel was written by an author who has experienced many turning points in his life, data on the most significant moments of his life and works created by him are indicated, among which "Çalığışu" occupies a special place.

We can see that in this novels description of woman. For example, in "Jane Eyre" novel tells that "Women are supposed to be very calm generally: but women feel just as men feel; they need exercise for their faculties, and a field for their efforts, as much as their brothers do; they suffer from too rigid a restraint, to absolute a

stagnation, precisely as men would suffer; and it is narrow-minded in their more privileged fellow-creatures to say that they ought to confine themselves to making puddings and knitting stockings, to playing on the piano and embroidering bags." by Jane Eyre[1]. Moreover, Charlotta Bronte represents the role of woman in the Victorian era. So, women, in all classes, were still living in a world which was misogynistic and male-dominated. Their purpose in life was to produce male heirs and maintain the home by hiring and overseeing servants. It was also taboo for one to marry significantly below one's social class. This is one reason that Jane is not a conventional heroine for the society of her time. Although, as a governess, she is not considered to be as low as a housemaid, she is still part of the hired help in the house. This is why it is unconventional for her and Mr Rochester to be in a relationship. Yet this is not as peculiar as how Jane Eyre ends their relationship due to her sense of betrayal. It would have been considered extremely foolish for a working-woman's sense of betrayal to end and turn down a man of great wealth.

Additionally, in "Cholikushi" novel tells that the life of a woman in Islamic society and how traditions begin to break down at the beginning of the century and new trends appear in relations between men and women. The main character rebelles against backward views and asserts her right to an independent life. She will have to face misunderstanding and go through many trials, but fortitude and a pure heart help her overcome them with honor. Thanks to this, the novel was received by Turkish women with great gratitude.

Conclusion.

A woman is a pillar of life, a follower of traditions. The woman magnifies the universe with her goddess. Her heart is full of beauty, with a woman's heart, beauty can be easily recognized as a twin concept. I can say that woman have a special place in the family and in society. Woman are the key to sustainable development and quality of life. They should act as leaders of the society to raise voice against women violence, exploitation in household as well as in workplace. Actually, it is

the women who have sustained the growth of society and moulded the future of notions.

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